

TURBOMACHINERY AERODYNAMIC AND AEROELASTIC PREDICTIONS WITH MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Aerodynamic and aeroelastic design of modern fans and compressors in turbomachines is conducted by simplified simulations and design rules resulting from years of experience; verification and certification are based on experimental testing and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. However, current engine designs have approached their limit in efficiency and noise, and to achieve significant improvements new design concepts are required (such as ultra-high-bypass ratio fans or open fans). The rules for aerodynamic and aeroelastic stability do not exist for these new design concepts, and hence, the role of simulations is now more relevant than ever. Numerical techniques based on CFD can be used for this purpose, but they are generally time-consuming and expensive for design space exploration and flow optimisation. Moreover, CFD methods require the modelling of turbulence which can be a key driver in aeroelastic vibrations. In this paper, the next generation of stability prediction framework for fans and compressors is proposed. This is achieved by integrating conventional numerical CFD methods, machine learning (ML) and domain knowledge to synergistically construct a Physically Guided Machine Learning (PGML) model for stability analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

EU goal of climate-neutral by 2050 requires revolutionary design concepts for aviation and power generation which do not result in safety and reliability issues. Aeroelastic and aerodynamic instabilities are at the origin of large deformations of structures and limit the ultra-efficient design of components in various industrial branches such as aviation and power generation. There has been an increase in the number of aeroelastic and aerodynamic failures over recent years which are the consequence of new design concepts used for reducing greenhouse emission.

Current aeroelastic and aerodynamic verification and certification are based on experimental testing by using sub-scale models which are not representative of real geometry, as not all the aerodynamic and aeroelastic non-dimensional parameters can be matched simultaneously. On the other hand, numerical

models which are based on coupled Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Finite Element Analyses (FEA) can be used for full-scale geometries at no additional cost compared to scaled models, but such analysis cannot be performed routinely during design stages. Moreover, aeroelastic events that commonly occur at off-design conditions involve unsteady separated flows, indicating that accurate simulation may require scale-resolving techniques such as Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) or Large Eddy Simulations (LES). At representative Reynolds number such computations are not practical for real engineering problems due to immense computational cost. Hence, improved Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) turbulence models for detached flows are required.

Aerodynamic design of gas turbines and jet engines relies on the assumption of infinitely accurate geometry and boundary conditions. Analytical models and CFD simulations are performed using these ideal conditions as input, as well as circumferential periodicity which assumes that all the blades are identical. However, the manufactured engine will always exhibit geometry variability due to the manufacturing process. The impact of this variability on the performances is of paramount importance. The effects of tip gap and stagger angle variations were analyzed in [1] through a series of CFD computations. Results from this paper illustrate that the stagger angle and tip gap variations can have a significant effect on efficiency (around 1%) and stall boundary (around 2%).

The effects of stagger variations around annulus (mis-staggering) and mistuning (frequency variation) on flutter stability of a fan blade were studied in [2]. The mis-stagger study showed that the relationship between mis-stagger level and aero-damping is complex, which depending on the stagger angle can be stabilizing or destabilizing. The mistuning results presented in this paper showed that mistuning had a substantial effect on the flutter stability of the fan blade and increasing level of mistuning increases flutter margin of the fan blade. Overall, the data in this paper clearly showed that manufacturing and environmental uncertainties can play an important role in the flutter stability of a fan blade. They demonstrate that aeroelastic similarity is not necessarily achieved if only aerodynamic properties and the traditional aeroelastic parameters, reduced

Fig. 1 Variations of aero-damping as a function of α

frequency and mass ratio, are maintained. The application of readily available Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) tools like Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) will suffer from the problem of “the curse of dimensionality”.

The pioneering work carried out on fan flutter [3-6] has identified two predominant blade flutter mechanisms, namely:

1. *Aero-acoustic driven flutter caused by reflections from intake*

At the flutter condition, the intake length and mean Mach number determine the propagation time and thus the phasing of the reflected acoustic wave, which can be beneficial or detrimental to the overall stability of the fan system. In [7] a simple model that can be used to study the effects of the intake on flutter was introduced and validated.

2. *Flow mode shape interaction driven flutter.*

Our previous experience has shown that the non-linearity and high dimensionality of aeroelastic problems defy an analytical approach for this element of fan stall flutter. An example of this is shown in **Fig. 1** where the variation of damping at various mass flows is plotted as a function of α [5], where α is defined as the ratio of twist over plunge in the mode shape. The numbers next to each curve denote the mass flow at that operating condition.

Considering the above, a new approach for aerodynamic and aeroelastic modelling is required. In the past decade, there has been a proliferation in the use of machine learning for improving turbulence models for aerodynamic performance predictions. However, more often than not, in the course of analysing complex fluid flows, the cost of data acquisition is prohibitive, which results in decision making under partial information. In this *small data* regime, most state-of-the-art machine learning techniques lack robustness, and convergence is not guaranteed. Hence, this growing area requires novel methodologies that are able to integrate traditional physics-based modelling with state-of-the-art machine learning (ML) techniques. In this paper a Physics-Guided Machine Learning (PGML) framework that

integrates traditional physics-based modelling with state-of-the-art machine learning data processing is introduced. The steady CFD prediction, which is paramount for providing training data in PGML, is obtained using an improved data-driven turbulence model. Successful achievement of this framework will lead to

- (1) A method which is more accurate than URANS solvers (as it is trained on high-fidelity data such as DNS and LES)
- (2) Computationally faster than RANS
- (3) It can model uncertainties.

In this paper, the proposed framework is first applied to the following tasks

- (1) Turbulence modelling
- (2) Manufacturing tolerances
- (3) Flutter modelling

which were identified as bottlenecks in current modelling methods. The data can come from experiment or simulation. Aeroelastic tests are expensive (especially in case of failure) and moreover, provide a limited amount of data in time and space. Therefore, numerical models based on CFD offer a cheaper and faster approach for data acquisition and will provide all desired quantities with a high resolution in space and time. The logic behind this approach is to develop an accurate CFD method (in *task 1*) which can be used for data generation in *task 2* and *task 3*. These three tasks are explained in the next 3 sections.

2. MACHINE LEARNING FOR TURBULENCE MODELING

Turbulence modelling plays a crucial role on predicting aerodynamic and aeroelastic instabilities of turbomachinery. Due to the multi-scale and multi-physics nature of these applications, the Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) simulation with a turbulence model has to be used for the industrial design/analysis workflow in the foreseeable future. These RANS turbulence models, however, were mostly developed in the 90s by human intelligence after observing small data, which are often deficient for compressor near-stall flows [8]. The uncertainty and empiricism involved during the development process of RANS turbulence models can be generally classified into four levels [9]:

- Level 1: the loss of fluctuating information during the ensemble averaging process, which is fundamentally irrecoverable.
- Level 2: assumptions made for the constitutive relation between the mean strain rate tensor and the Reynolds stress tensor (e.g., Boussinesq assumption for eddy viscosity models).
- Level 3: assumptions made for the formulation of the turbulence model transport equation(s).
- Level 4: uncertainties during the calibration process of the model coefficients.

With the recent accumulation of high-fidelity turbulence data and advancement of machine learning (ML) in scientific simulation, there is a growing interest in developing a data-driven turbulence model that can potentially improve the established turbulence models at Level 2, 3 and 4. Pioneering works include but not limited to Ling et al. [10], Weatheritt et al. [11] and Wang et al. [12] at Level 2; Singh et al. [13] at Level 3;

(a) shock front location x_{sf} and separation size L_s of transonic bump

(b) stall margin of NASA Rotor 67

Fig. 2 Parametric uncertainty of Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model coefficients

Edeling et al. [14] at Level 4. For a complete review, the readers are redirected to Duraisamy [9].

From the perspective of turbulence model developers, an ML correction at upper levels has the best potential in improving the model accuracy because the empiricism and error will not build up in the next level. However, the challenges of such an approach are the numerical stability [15] and the reusability, i.e., an ML model trained on one geometry/operating condition can be robustly applied to other geometries/operating conditions with improved or equally good accuracy compared to that without the ML correction. From the perspective of turbulence model users, an ML correction at lower levels is more favoured due to the robustness concern, but it may not provide adequate improvement in prediction accuracy.

In searching for the best ML solution for turbulence modelling of compressor near-stall flows, several research has been performed on the Spalart-Allmaras (SA) one-equation model:

- (1) uncertainty quantification of turbulence model coefficients (Level 4)
- (2) proposal of a turbo-oriented data-driven turbulence model form (Level 3)
- (3) explainability of an ML-assisted turbulence model (Level 3)

These works will be introduced in detail in the following subsections.

2.1 Uncertainty Quantification of Turbulence Model Coefficients

The coefficients of established turbulence models were often calibrated using data of simple shear flow and attached boundary layer flow. Due to the calibration nature, a broad range of coefficient values is capable of reproducing the high-fidelity data of these simple flows, but only one set of coefficients was chosen as the default. The coefficients within the calibration range, however, may yield evident differences in predicting industrial flows featured by strong pressure gradient and 3D separation. Hence, parametric uncertainty arises (Level 4).

A potential method to reduce the parametric uncertainty is to use ML-adapting model coefficients within the calibration range (e.g., [16]). To unveil the potential of such an approach in

predicting compressor near-stall flows, a series of uncertainty quantification (UQ) works have been performed in simple 2D separated flows, 2D airfoil stall and 3D compressor stall [17][18]. The UQ framework is based on a metamodel-based Monte Carlo method, where the fully connected neural networks (FCNN) serve as the metamodel that directly maps the turbulence model coefficients with the quantities of interest (QoI).

Representative UQ results are presented in **Fig. 2**. For the 2D axisymmetric transonic bump case shown in **Fig. 2(a)**, it was found that the shock front location and the separation size cannot be predicted simultaneously accurately by tuning the model coefficients, i.e., a trade-off between different QoIs exist. For the 3D NASA Rotor 67 case shown in **Fig. 2(b)**, the parametric uncertainty band cannot envelop the measured data, indicating tuning the model coefficients is not sufficient to predict the stall margin accurately.

Based on the UQ metamodel, the sensitivity of each model coefficient can also be quantified. Among all the investigated separated flows, the coefficients σ and c_{bl} were found consistently more significant than the rest coefficients; the larger the separation size (i.e., a larger angle of attack for airfoils, a smaller mass flow for compressors, etc.), the more significant σ and c_{bl} become [18]. These coefficients are directly related to the source terms, which implies the potential of using ML to correct the source terms of the turbulence model transport equation(s).

In summary, an ML correction of the model coefficients alone is not sufficient to predict compressor near-stall flows accurately, and an ML-correction to the model form is needed.

2.2 A Turbo-Oriented Data-Driven Turbulence Model Form

The formulations of established eddy viscosity RANS turbulence models are often based on two assumptions: (1) a linear relation between the strain rate and the Reynolds stress component is assumed in the constitutive relation at Level 2; (2) the equilibrium turbulence condition is assumed in the transport equation(s) of the turbulence model at Level 3. These assumptions are sufficiently accurate in simple flows, but they may not apply to industrial flows and thus the model form uncertainty at Level 2 and 3.

To evaluate the efficacy of corrections at Level 2 and 3, established empirical modifications to the SA model were compared in a transonic axial compressor [19]. It was found that corrections at Level 3, e.g., modifications to the transport equation with respect to the features of rotation and curvature, helicity, and pressure gradient, are able to improve the prediction on the tip blockage cell and thus the stall margin. Correction at Level 2, e.g., a quadratic constitutive relation (QCR), has limited effects on the compressor near-tip flows. Concurrent research [20] has also evaluated empirical modified SA model forms in a linear compressor cascade featured by corner separation, and both corrections at Level 2 and 3 are effective in improving the prediction accuracy. The studies above indicate that an ML correction at Level 3 is promising for compressor near-stall flows considering both efficacy and robustness; an ML correction at Level 2 can still be effective if higher order terms were involved in the constitutive relation, but more evidence is needed from future research. In this work, an ML correction at Level 3 is pursued.

In the recent work of the authors [21], a turbo-oriented data-driven modification to the SA model was proposed for better prediction of compressor near-stall flows. Specifically, the model formulations were inspired from observations of turbomachinery flow features, and the model coefficients were calibrated using turbomachinery flow data.

From the observations of compressor separated flow topology of tip leakage vortex and hub corner separation vortex, an empirical blockage identifier term was proposed, which is based on the dimensionless vortical pressure gradient (hence the name “SA-PG_ω”). This term can effectively identify compressor blockage cells featured by 3D swirling, adverse pressure gradient and low momentum flows, whereas in 2D canonical flows the term is automatically switched off to zero. The empirical blockage identifier is then used to boost the local eddy viscosity, which reduces the blockage size and thus extends the stall boundary.

Considering the uncertainties involved in the experiment and CFD of turbomachinery, the model coefficients were calibrated by a Bayesian inference approach. The NASA Rotor 67 radial profile data at the peak efficiency and the near stall conditions of the design speed were used for calibration. The calibration workflow is illustrated in Fig. 3. In the first place, a database of the coefficients was generated and simulated by CFD, and the accuracy of each coefficient set is measured. An FCNN was then trained as the metamodel of the CFD, which provides fast prediction of model accuracy given the coefficients. Lastly, Bayesian inference was applied to find the most likely coefficient set that gives the best accuracy.

The proposed SA-PG_ω model was validated extensively in four compressors, namely NASA Rotor 67, TUDa-GLR-OpenStage, BUAA Stage B rotor and LMFA NACA65 cascade. The first two cases have industrial levels of Reynolds number and Mach number, and that of the last two cases are at the laboratory level. Although the model coefficients were calibrated using only the radial profile data of two operating points, the SA-PG_ω model can significantly improve the prediction of the stall margin at the whole performance map (e.g., NASA Rotor 67 shown in Fig. 3) and the blockage size (e.g., BUAA Stage B rotor shown in Fig. 4). Thus, the SA-PG_ω model is recommended as

Fig. 3 Workflow of SA-PG_ω model coefficient calibration based on FCNN and Bayesian inference

Fig. 4 Validation of SA-PG_ω model on predicting the tip blockage cell of BUAA Stage B rotor

an update of the previous SA-HPG, SA-PG and SA-H models for predictions of compressor near-stall flows.

2.3 Explainability of an ML-Assisted Turbulence Model

To obtain a predictive turbulence model for both industrial and canonical flows, multiple flow features need to be considered at the same time. Such a modelling task is intractable for human turbulence model developers, but it is comparatively easier using ML. A typical approach is to use an ML model to construct a functional mapping between the input flow features and the output discrepancies of turbulence quantities (e.g., Reynolds stress anisotropy [12], eddy viscosity [13], etc.). However, such an approach may be argued as a “black-box”, because the model response with respect to the change of each flow feature and the interaction between different flow features

(a) summary of SHAP analysis. Left: bar chart of the mean absolute SHAP value (i.e., global significance of a feature). Right: bee swarm plots of SHAP values. Each dot corresponds to a CFD grid point, with the horizontal location representing the SHAP value ϕ_i (impact of feature q_i on the RF prediction) and the color representing the feature value q_i at that grid point. When multiple points locate at the same horizontal position, they pile up in the vertical direction to show the occurrence probability density.

(b) dependency plot of feature values versus diagonal SHAP interaction values (i.e., pure effect of a feature to the RF prediction).

Fig. 5 Explaining an ML-assisted turbulence model using the post-hoc method SHAP

are vague. The lack of explainability undermines human users' trust in the model, which hinders its application in real world problems.

In the recent work of the authors [22], two types of methods to improve the explainability of an ML-assisted turbulence model were proposed, namely the intrinsic methods and the post-hoc methods. The ML-assisted turbulence model framework uses a random forest (RF) model to construct the functional mapping between the input flow features and the output eddy viscosity discrepancy. The investigated flow case is the 2D axisymmetric transonic bump featured by shock-boundary layer interaction.

The intrinsic methods reduce the complexity of the ML model, i.e., the simpler the ML model form, the more explainable it becomes. This method includes a physics-free hyperparameter study and a physics-based input feature selection study. From the hyperparameter study, a pareto front between model complexity (i.e., explainability) and model accuracy was found, and a cost-effect hyperparameter set can reduce the model complexity significantly without evident loss of model accuracy. From the input feature selection study, it was demonstrated that removing redundant flow features can reduce the model complexity without evident loss of model accuracy.

The post-hoc methods use model-agnostic tools to analyse the ML model behaviour. They can help identify the causal link between the inputs and the outputs and the interaction among different inputs. In this work, the state-of-the-art post-hoc method named Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) [23] was demonstrated.

The main results of the SHAP analysis are presented in **Fig. 5**. From the global analysis of the SHAP value shown in the bar plot of **Fig. 5(a)**, a ranked list of input flow features regarding its

global significance is obtained, where the features of viscosity ratio, strain versus vorticity, wall proximity and pressure gradient versus normal shear stress were shown important. From the bee swarm plot of **Fig. 5(a)**, the distribution of each flow feature in the investigated flow case is shown, and the correlation between the feature value (i.e., horizontal location) and the feature contribution to the RF output (i.e., color) can be qualitatively identified.

To unveil the causal link between the input flow feature and the RF output, the diagonal SHAP interaction values (i.e., pure effect of a feature) are plotted against the feature values in **Fig. 5(b)**. These plots clearly show the monotonic relations between some of the q_i and $\phi_{i,i}$, e.g., $\Delta v_t \propto q_9$, $-q_4$, q_8 , q_3 . Specifically, the trained ML model discovered: (1) the well-known scaling between eddy viscosity and its source term, which was originally found from dimensional analysis; (2) the well-known rotation and shear effects on the eddy viscosity source term, which was explicitly written in the Reynolds stress transport equations; and (3) the pressure normal stress and normal shear stress effect on the eddy viscosity source term, which has not attracted much attention in previous research.

3. MACHINE LEARNING FOR MANUFACTURING TOLERANCES

The effect of geometrical variability on performances is of prior importance for the design of jet engines. In modern transonic compressors and fans, changes in stagger angle have a strong impact on efficiency, stall margin [24] and flutter margin [2]. To evaluate those effects at a reasonable cost, a surrogate model which relies on a reduced order model has been developed. The performances of any rotor assembly (i.e. a set of ordered blades with different stagger angles) is predicted by

using single and double passage computations. Single passage results give the effect of mean stagger angle, whereas double passage results give the effect of adjacent mis-stagger. The approach has been tested on NASA Rotor 67.

To represent stagger angle manufacturing tolerances, a twist is imposed on the blade by using mesh morphing. Following previous work [24], the variation of stagger angle is in the range of $\pm 1.5^\circ$. To model tip gap variations, five meshes are generated with five different gaps, ranging from 0.3mm to 1.5mm (50% to 250% of the nominal tip gap).

The goal of the surrogate model is to output the characteristic curve of a compressor at a given speed knowing the blade distribution pattern around the annulus. First, a blade arrangement is chosen. Once an ordered blade distribution is defined, the model sweeps through each pair of adjacent blades and computes the characteristic curve of an equivalent compressor, consisting of these two blades arranged in an alternated pattern. To obtain the performances of the targeted blade arrangement, the equivalent compressor's characteristic curves are mass averaged. The mass flow \dot{m} , the total pressure ratio PR and the isentropic efficiency η are given by:

$$\dot{m} = \frac{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i}{N}; PR = \frac{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i PR_i}{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i}; \eta = \frac{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i \eta_i}{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i}$$

where N is the number of blades, \dot{m} the mass flow, PR_i the total pressure ratio and η_i the isentropic efficiency of the equivalent compressor consisting of blades i and $i + 1$. The influence on blades further apart ($i - 2$ and $i + 2$) is neglected.

A convergence study has shown that the proposed surrogate model gives a good accuracy for stagger angle variations [25]. Characteristic curves are computed for different stagger angles and linear interpolation is used to recover any value of the average stagger angle.

For tip variations, nonlinear effects on stall margin and performance are observed. In that case, simple linear interpolation is sufficient to build a reliable surrogate model. To overcome this issue, free parameters ($\alpha, \beta, \kappa, \delta$) have been added to the averaging process to consider the nonlinear effects. A new formula, which is referred to as smart average, is instead used.

$$PR_s = \frac{\sum_i^N \alpha \dot{m}_i^\beta PR_i^\kappa}{\sum_i^N \dot{m}_i^\delta}$$

Using full annulus computations as target values, the parameters are computed using a non-linear least square optimization. The efficiency of the smart average technique is shown in Fig. 6.

Uncertainty quantification has been used to assess the variability of the nominal design of Rotor 67 with respect to manufacturing tolerances. In [25], uniform continuous distributions of stagger variations between -1.5 and $+1.5$ and uniform discrete tip gap variations (5 equally spaced values between 0.2% span and 1% span) have been considered. 50,000 thousand sets of blades have been generated. Each set of blades has then been assembled in any order, resulting in one rotor configuration. In the end, three different arrangements of the blades have been studied in detail:

- random, representative of not measuring blade geometry
- sinusoidal, minimizing the variation between adjacent blades
- zigzag, maximizing the variation between adjacent blades

Fig. 6 Comparison of standard and smart average surrogate model with full annulus CFD for NASA Rotor 67

Fig. 7 Different arrangements for a given set of 22 blades with stagger angle variation

The sinusoidal and the zigzag arrangements have been obtained by reformulating the optimisation problem as an equivalent travelling salesman problem (finding the shortest path

Fig. 8 Envelope of maximum isentropic efficiency against average stagger angle (a) and tip gap (b) for three different arrangements for NASA Rotor 67

crossing a given set of cities, the distance between them being known). The resulting equivalent travelling salesman problem was solved using a genetic algorithm. An example of an arrangement is shown in Fig. 7.

The effect of the arrangement for stagger variations is shown in Fig. 8 (a). Arranging the blades in a sinusoidal pattern guarantees the narrowest envelope, whereas it is the widest for the zigzag pattern. The width of the envelope for random arrangement is similar to the zigzag arrangement envelope, indicating large sensitivity to the blade arrangement. The random arrangement is representative of a process for which no strategy is chosen or for which no information on manufactured blade geometry is available. The effect of the arrangement for tip variations is shown in Fig. 8 (b). For tip gap variations, the best performances are given by the zigzag arrangement while the worst ones are obtained using the sinusoidal pattern. More interestingly, the range of efficiency depends on the chosen arrangement.

These results can be linked with mistuning analysis to find the best pattern for robustly optimising performance, stall margin and flutter margin. It has been shown in [26] that intentional mistuning has a positive effect on flutter margin and it is possible to find the best arrangement pattern. In Fig. 9 we can see that

Fig. 9 Stability map as a function of amplitude of mistuning and harmonic pattern mistuning at mass flows of $m=0.91$ with intake for a 20-blade compressor [26]

sinusoidal (ND 1) and zig-zag (ND 10) are good candidates for improving flutter margin. The surrogate model developed in [26] based on AIC and SNM can be easily coupled to the proposed surrogate model for manufacturing tolerances.

4. MACHINE LEARNING FOR FLUTTER MODELLING

Aeroelastic stability is of paramount importance when designing a new fan or compressor blade. The task of assessing blade stability is made ever more relevant by the recent trend towards blisks, which are characterised by nearly zero structural damping. Stall flutter is among the plethora of aeroelastic phenomena that can limit the range, reliability and safety of turbomachinery operation and it has been extensively studied with analytical, experimental and computational methods. Stall flutter is usually associated with high steady loading, low reduced frequency for blades vibrating in first bending, flap or twist modes. Moreover, recent computational studies have shown that the nature of acoustic waves inside the duct can influence aerodynamic damping. Flutter is, therefore, influenced by steady and unsteady flow features, aeroacoustics and structural properties. Although these properties are well understood, at early design stages, most of the attention is focused on performance, while aeroelastic stability is investigated only in terms of simple parameters such as reduced frequency. The influence of flow variables and structural parameters is assessed later in the process and the evaluation of blade stability is left to linear or nonlinear CFD methods. The investigation of different flow regimes, frequencies, mode shapes and nodal diameters is an expensive, but necessary process which leads to an accumulation of aeroelastic data that, usually, is not utilised further than the calculation of the figure of merit, that is, aerodynamic damping. The authors propose machine learning techniques to leverage aeroelastic data and enhance its usefulness beyond unsteady flow analysis and aerodynamic damping calculations. In both the following studies, a simplified 2D geometry is used to demonstrate the validity of the frameworks, the data is obtained with a linearised

Fig. 10 Comparison of FCNN (dashed red line) and CFD (solid black line) predictions.

flow solver and the range of input coefficients are chosen to be relevant for compressor and fan blades.

In [27], the authors perform a sensitivity analysis of aerodynamic damping based on simple parameters. These relevant parameters are based on the literature: inlet Mach number, M_1 , incidence angle, β_1 , reduced frequency k , bending-twist ratio of mode shape X_t , where 0 and infinity correspond to a pure twist and a pure bending respectively, and Interblade Phase Angle, σ . The sensitivity analysis is carried out by means of a FCNN (fully connected neural network) surrogate model. The databases needed to train the surrogate model are created by means of Latin Hypercube Sampling method and the quantity of interest, that is the output of the surrogate model, is aerodynamic damping.

The model is validated against test data from CFD for different flow regimes. **Fig. 10(a)** shows that for a blade vibrating in flap mode, in transonic flow, aerodynamic damping decreases with increasing flow incidence. The flow conditions for this case are very similar to what a fan blade section would experience as it moves up a constant speed characteristic. The surrogate model is able to follow the trend of the CFD closely, and to predict the flutter boundary within 0.2 degrees, confirming that its predictions can be trusted for engineering-relevant cases. **Fig. 10(b)** shows a sweep of Interblade Phase Angle; the FCNN is able to follow the CFD closely, the peaks in aerodynamic damping due to acoustic resonance are well predicted both in location and magnitude and so is the overall shape of the curve.

The FCNN is fully differentiable, which means that gradients w.r.t. input parameters can be calculated. Take a blade behaving like **Fig. 10(b)** as a test case. Two intervals of σ are affected by flutter: 0 to 30 and 60 to 140. The objective is to adjust the design parameters so that instability can be avoided. In order to achieve this goal, one can compute gradients, and use them as a guide for deciding the best action to take in order to increase damping in an unstable configuration. The normalised gradients at $\sigma=20$ and $\sigma=120$ are shown in **Fig. 11**. The bar height, value of normalised gradient, is a measure of aerodynamic damping sensitivity, while the sign on top gives the type of correlation between input and output. One can see that, varying only one parameter, the most effective action one can take (for both Interblade Phase Angles) is to reduce the incidence of incoming flow onto the blade (e.g., restaggering the blade). In particular, the surrogate model predicts that a decrease of 1.8 degrees in flow incidence should stabilise the blade.

A restaggered case is set up in CFD to confirm the surrogate model predictions (**Fig. 12**). Computational methods are

Fig. 11 FCNN gradients w.r.t. input variables and change in damping with incidence and frequency.

Fig. 12 CFD prediction of damping for “restaggered” blade.

deterministic in nature, but are affected by errors and sensitivities which cause loss of robustness in the results and can be assimilated as uncertainty. Modelling errors might arise when the investigated flow condition breaks the assumptions of the model itself, moreover, especially in transonic flow, slight changes in steady flow variables can lead to a substantially different unsteady flow. In [28], the authors tackle the tasks of producing new predictions of aerodynamic damping and their associated confidence intervals, as a form of uncertainty quantification, simultaneously, by means of a machine learning surrogate model based on [29]. The model is trained on a similar database similar to the one employed in [27], described in this case in terms of relevant physical features rather than simple parameters, such as cutoff ratios, mass flow rate and pressure ratio. The predictive performance of the model is tested on a validation set of computations and the quality of the confidence intervals is investigated by measuring the resulting coverage fraction.

In **Fig. 13**, two types of uncertainties are shown. The first panel shows aerodynamic damping against pressure ratio; the region of steep aerodynamic damping decrease is characterised by shock induced separation at high angle of attack, which is an inherently unsteady condition characterised by small amplitude shock movement. This flow condition is extremely sensitive to the imposed pressure ratio, a small deviation from the target mass flow and pressure ratio can highly affect the computed aerodynamic damping, therefore the surrogate model predicts large confidence intervals in that region. The second panel shows aerodynamic damping against interblade phase angle; here there is a very good agreement between model and CFD, but it is

(a) Damping against pressure ratio at fixed mass flow

(b) Damping against IBPA at fixed operating conditions

Fig. 13 Comparison between CFD and surrogate model with confidence intervals

Fig. 14 CFD (red) and surrogate model (blue) flutter boundaries

interesting to see how the confidence intervals become larger in size as the cut-off frequencies are approached. This trend is also driven by a form of sensitivity, but, whereas the previous tests have shown the influence of shock induced separation, in this case the strong response to changes in flow field is acoustic in nature. Having shown the effectiveness of confidence intervals in evaluating aerodynamic damping uncertainties, the proposed method is applied to determine a safer flutter boundary for the cascade using the low end of the confidence intervals. **Fig. 14** shows the compressor map of the cascade with flutter boundaries from CFD and from the surrogate model.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a framework for using data driven approach for improving CFD prediction of aerodynamic and aeroelastic stability is proposed. The idea behind this framework is to improve the CFD prediction capability (in terms of turbulence model) and then use CFD to generate data for stability prediction model. The presented studies leverage relatively small datasets that, with current computational power, can be obtained quickly, and show how ML methods and data analysis techniques can

further our understanding of flow phenomena and our capability of design. Initial results are encouraging and show that :

- 1- SA turbulence model stall predication capability can be improved significantly by using a data-driven approach using high fidelity CFD or measured data. The SA-PG_o model is based on the dimensionless vortical pressure gradient, which identifies 3D swirling low-momentum blockage cells in compressor passages and boosts the local eddy viscosity; whereas in 2D canonical flows, the modification is automatically switched-off. The new model coefficients are calibrated by Bayesian inference using the NASA Rotor 67 radial profile data at the PE and NS conditions of the design speed.
- 2- An efficient surrogate model for predicting the effects of manufacturing tolerances on compressor performance and stability is developed. The algorithm relies on the physical assumption that most of the effect is on the blade itself and its neighbours, whereas the influence of further blades can be neglected. The surrogate model showed good agreement with CFD data.
- 3- Two machine learnt models for flutter have been presented. Both models fit at the end of an early design loop and can be used to enhance point value predictions of aerodynamic damping. First, an FCNN model is used to extract gradients for sensitivity analysis and redesign of an existing blade; second, a random forest based model is used to obtain confidence intervals of damping, and a safer flutter boundary accounting for uncertainties in the data.

In the next phase, the three research areas will be integrated to form a ML aided framework for flutter prediction which can be used at early design stages. The accuracy of the flutter prediction framework can be improved by means of physics guided machine learning.

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